

Experimental method for determining the atomistic details of the Quantum-well interface

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Abstract: In this work, we determine the carrier-concentration, low-temperature electron-mobility and valley-splitting, in sub-surface Si/SiGe quantum wells, typically used to define physical spin qubits, via measurement of (temperature-dependent) Quantum Hall effect and Shubnikov De-Haas oscillations.

1. Introduction

The scalable architecture for silicon spin-quantum-computing (SQC) relies on surface-gated, electrostatically-induced quantum dots (QDs) in sub-surface Si/SiGe quantum wells, to host the spin qubits. For the Hilbert space of the Zeeman qubit to be fiducially defined, it is imperative to have the 6-fold valley-degeneracy of the Silicon conduction band completely lifted. While tensile strain in the Si quantum well (QW) lifts the degeneracy between the two valleys perpendicular to and the four valleys parallel to the QW-plane, the degeneracy between the two lower-lying out-of-plane valleys is further lifted by quantum confinement, thus rendering the QD-ground-state non-degenerate [1, 2]. However, the extent of valley splitting is highly sensitive to the quality of the QW-interface with its barrier, and applied electric fields [2].

In this work, we record quantum Hall and Shubnikov de-Haas (SdH) data from a sub-surface undoped Si/SiGe QW, typically used to define surface-gated QDs, to estimate carrier density, low-temperature electron mobility and the valley splitting. We also discuss some anomalous features observed in the Quantum Hall data recorded from a few of the samples.

2. The Si/SiGe heterostructure, Hall-bar design and fabrication

A transmission electron microscope (TEM) image of the strained silicon QW, embedded within SiGe barriers, is shown in Figure 1 (a). The Si QW is 30 nm below the surface. To fabricate the Hall bars, Ohmic contacts are created by a combination of photolithography, phosphorus ion-implantation, post-implantation annealing and Ti/Au deposition, by electron beam evaporation. An 80-nm chemical-vapor-deposition-(CVD)-grown SiO₂ separates the ohmic contacts from the surface gate for carrier accumulation, patterned in the Hall bar geometry (Figure 1 (b)). The gate pattern has also been obtained by photolithography and Ti/Au deposition.

Figure 1: Hall Bar Fabrication. (a) Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of the buried Si Q-well embedded in Si/SiGe heterostructure. (b) Optical micrograph of the completed Hall bar device, with Length to Width ratio of 9.

3. Quantum Hall Measurement

The Hall and longitudinal resistances of the Hall bar have been measured by standard lock-in techniques, in a Bluefors LD400 dilution refrigerator, maintained at a base temperature of 8 mK, and equipped with a superconducting solenoid magnet, with a maximum field strength of 9 T. The data recorded from the sample shown in Figure 1 (b), for a fixed value of the accumulation gate voltage, is shown in Figure 2 (a). SdH oscillations are clearly visible in the R_{xx} data. The gate-voltage-dependence of the carrier concentration is shown in Figure 2 (b), while Figure 2 (c) shows the estimated electron mobility as a function of the gate voltage.

Figure 2: Hall-bar characterization. (a) Hall (blue) and longitudinal (red) resistance measured as a function of magnetic field, (b) the longitudinal (red) resistance plotted as a function of inverse magnetic field and (c) the carrier concentration and mobility as functions of the accumulation-gate voltage.

Surprisingly, instead of the usual resistance-quantum steps, the R_{xy} plot also shows SdH-like oscillations. This may be attributed to intermixing of the longitudinal and Hall components in the transverse direction [2]. Accordingly, we increased the width of the same Hall bar, as shown in Figure 3 (a), but the trend remained the same (Figure 3 (b)). Also, a careful observation reveals that the maxima of the R_{xy} plot coincides with the minima of the R_{xx} , over the magnetic field range of 2.5 T (Figure 3 (c)). This indicates that the anomalous behavior observed in these samples is most likely related to formation of compressible and incompressible regions within the Hall bar, together with the interference of valley splitting [2, 3]. A more careful investigation of the phenomenon is currently underway.

Figure 3: Anomalous Hall and SdH plots (a) Optical micrograph of the Hall-bar device, where the width of the channel is increased to obtain a L/W ratio of 1.4. (b) Hall (blue) and longitudinal (red) resistance measured as a function of magnetic field (c) Close-up plot of Figure 3 (b) in the range of magnetic field, $B = 0$ to 2.5 T.

5. Discussion on the estimation of valley splitting

For determination of valley-splitting, the requirement is to identify minima in SdH data, which correspond to odd filling factors, at magnetic fields high enough such that the valley splitting is sufficiently larger than the thermal broadening of the Landau levels. Once identified, the SdH minima may be tracked as a function of the sample temperature, which yields the valley splitting (at a particular magnetic field/ filling factor) based on the following equation: $R_{xx}(T) \propto e^{-E_v/k_B T}$. The valley splitting, E_v , may then be determined for different voltages on the accumulation gate, or equivalently, at different electron density in the QW.

4. References

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